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Community energy as care infrastructure: Insights from two energy communities in England and Greece

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ABSTRACT

This article examines community energy projects as infrastructures of care, exploring how they address interconnected environmental and social challenges. While grassroots renewable energy projects are often framed in technical or economic terms, we argue that their significance also lies in the relational, ethical and political dimensions of energy provision. Drawing on feminist care ethics, and particularly Tronto's phases of care, we analyse how community energy initiatives cultivate attentiveness to environmental concerns, assume responsibility for collective energy needs, support vulnerable households, and foster democratic participation. Empirically, we draw on qualitative research on two community energy projects in England and Greece. Through interviews with founders, members and supporting organizations, we show that these initiatives operate as care infrastructures that redistribute not only energy but also knowledge, capabilities and forms of solidarity. In doing so, they challenge dominant market-oriented understandings of energy and foreground principles of sufficiency, interdependence and shared responsibility. We conclude that by embedding care into energy production and consumption, community energy projects reconfigure everyday energy practices, expand democratic control and contribute to more just and sustainable futures.

1. Introduction

Energy policy across Europe and beyond is increasingly articulated through the imperatives of decarbonisation, net zero and renewable energy transitions. These shifts respond to the accelerating climate crisis, yet they are unfolding amid rising energy costs and worsening housing precarity [1,2]. The result is a deepening of energy poverty, commonly understood as inadequate access to essential energy services [3–6], a condition that encompasses not only economic constraints but also infrastructural deficits and wider social, educational and health inequalities [3]. Closely related is energy vulnerability, defined as the propensity of households to become incapable of securing the socially and materially required level of domestic energy [3,7].

The recent cost-of-living crises, intensified by the Covid-19 pandemic [8] and the war in Ukraine, have further amplified energy vulnerability across Europe [9], exposing the fragility of fossil fuel dependent systems while simultaneously underscoring the urgency of renewable energy transitions [10]. Questions of energy access and affordability are thus increasingly entangled with broader struggles around housing, social reproduction and the right to the city [11]. Against this backdrop,

grassroots energy initiatives, such as renewable energy cooperatives and community-owned projects, have emerged as important sites of socio-technical experimentation. These initiatives are frequently framed through the lens of energy democracy [12], understood as a call for more just, participatory and sustainable energy systems [13]. However, as this article demonstrates, they also intertwine energy provision with care-oriented practices that support households in the context of a deepening polycrisis.

Central to this perspective is the role of local communities and grassroots organizations in addressing energy poverty and environmental degradation by providing participatory, low-cost and sustainable alternatives to centralised energy systems [14]. Grassroots innovations, such as community-owned renewable energy projects, including solar cooperatives [15,16], enable households to access clean energy, reduce energy costs and improve living conditions. These initiatives redistribute control over energy resources, foster collective governance and often benefit marginalized groups underserved by traditional utilities.

Building on this literature, we argue that energy communities should be understood not only as reactive responses to crisis but also as prefigurative, care-oriented infrastructures. By reclaiming urban commons,

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reshaping everyday geographies, and constructing translocal solidarity networks, they cultivate alternative spaces of care. At the same time, their proliferation indicates that local actions can reverberate across scales. Renewable energy cooperatives and other energy communities can converge, learn from one another and potentially scale out to address challenges that are global in scope [17]. Local experiences may thus become catalysts for broader socioenvironmental transformations, embodying the emancipatory potential of grassroots mobilisation [18]. Yet, the politics of these initiatives remain ambivalent: community energy projects may inadvertently reproduce growth-oriented logics and market imperatives, thereby reinforcing the very crises they seek to confront [19].

To advance this discussion, we turn to the concept of care. Following Fisher and Tronto [20, p. 40], whose definition has been influential for thinking care beyond its conceptualization in relation to gendered invisibilised labour, we understand care as “*a species activity that includes everything that we do to maintain, continue, and repair our world so that we can live in it as well as possible. That world includes our bodies, ourselves, and our environment, all of which we seek to interweave in a complex, life sustaining web*”. We focus on the collectivization and democratization of energy production and consumption as a concrete manifestation of such care infrastructures. Bringing together literatures on community energy [21–24] and infrastructures of care [25–28] and drawing on empirical research on energy communities in Greece and the UK, we ask: How do grassroots energy projects act as infrastructures of care that advance counter-hegemonic values oriented toward democracy, the commons and social equality? We address this question by a) briefly reviewing literature on community energy, with particular attention to its socio-political aspects, b) linking these debates to the concept of care and caring infrastructure while presenting emerging scholarship on the energy-care nexus, and c) offering empirical insights interpreted through Tronto's [29] revised phases of care: caring about, taking care of, care giving, care receiving and caring with.

By situating energy communities within the entangled socio-environmental crises of our times, and by reinterpreting their practices through the lens of care, we argue that community energy projects can move beyond short-term relief to reconfigure everyday life and confront climate change, while opening up democratic and collectively transformative pathways for just energy transitions.

2. Theoretical framework

2.1. Community energy projects: Politicisation and scale

Over the last decades, a growing body of literature has explored grassroots innovations that address energy poverty and support the transition to renewable energy, showing different characteristics across geographical contexts. These initiatives engage citizens, small organizations and public institutions in collective energy production and consumption. In England, where one of our cases is based, alternative energy initiatives have historical roots stretching back to the 1970s [30], with community-led sustainable energy projects expanding particularly over the last two decades. Scholars note that many of these initiatives predate mainstream policy support, emerging from radical movements experimenting with democratic and socially oriented pathways to sustainability transitions [31]. On the other hand, in Greece, cooperative energy communities do not have such a long tradition, and many organizations legally formed as energy communities are for-profit entities that take advantage of the favourable conditions, whereas energy communities for self-consumption are a more recent trend [32].

The term *community energy* encompasses a wide variety of definitions and practices. Seyfang et al. [33] situate it within grassroots-led innovations, including initiatives ranging from renewable energy generation to community hall refurbishments and collective behaviour change programmes. Walker and Devine-Wright [34] emphasize projects in which communities, defined by place or interest, exhibit high

degrees of ownership, control and collective benefit. Similarly, Mah [35] highlights community-based efforts to reorganize local energy systems through distributed energy resources and efficiency practices. Alternative terms, including *clean energy community* [36], *community renewable energy* [24], *collective and politically motivated renewable energy projects* [37] reflect those conceptual and institutional differences. Other strands highlight more specific models such as *community solar* [38] or *local energy communities* [10], referring to forms of community energy centred on solar infrastructures owned by multiple, regionally based stakeholders, yet designed to remain socially inclusive and locally distributed. In the more recent literature, attention has shifted toward *energy communities* defined as networks of citizens collaborating in the generation, distribution, trade or storage of renewable energy, frequently structured as cooperatives. These initiatives prioritize decentralisation and citizen empowerment and often aim to provide environmental as well as social and economic benefits alongside energy access [9].

Yet scholars caution that not all energy projects claiming to be community-led necessarily prioritize social and environmental care, but the politicisation of energy projects remains an open question. The breadth of definitions within the field can allow initiatives to exploit the “community” label for individual or corporate gain [33], while the involvement of private companies may shift priorities toward profit-maximisation [10], thereby undermining principles of energy democracy and solidarity [24]. Sustaining the democratic, participatory and care-driven ethos of these infrastructures thus requires constant negotiation. As Tsagkari et al. [39] point out, economic growth is directly dependent on energy use, closely tied to capitalist modes of production and the lifestyles they promote. Attempts to decouple economic growth from energy consumption have proven ineffective and as Petrovics and Savini [19] argue despite recent efforts toward rapid and scalable decarbonisation, energy consumption has continued to rise in recent years, mirroring the broader growth trajectories of Western economies. This trend underscores the need to critically reassess the relationship between economic growth and energy demand and view energy democratization as a political question bounded to developmental trajectories.

In order to contribute meaningfully to broader social and environmental transformations, community energy projects need to evolve and expand, while navigating multiple local-global tensions. A central debate concerns how such initiatives can scale up, scale wide, or scale out. As Bonfert [10] points out, highly regulated energy production and distribution limit experimentation with innovative practices and often confines communities to indirect incentives for participation. At the same time, community energy infrastructures depend on non-local materials and global supply chains, frequently entangled in human rights violations and environmental harms [19], bringing renewed attention to questions of scale. Scholars highlight the potential for scaling through collaboration between energy commons and public institutions, recognising the importance of the human scale in energy commons, underscoring the need to strengthen solidarity and environmental justice [17]. Kunze and Becker [37] similarly argue that alternatives must be understood as both global and local, while Petrovics et al. [40] call for a more diverse understanding of scaling. Engaging with Tsing's [41] seminal article “On Nonscalability”, Kostakis et al. [42] challenge conventional approaches to scale that rely on standardisation, model replication and the erasure of local complexity. They propose instead a more sustainable ‘cosmolocal’ model of scalability, based on global design and local manufacturing, while Giotitsas et al. [43] explore this logic in the case of energy systems, calling for stronger collaborations between engineers and social scientists to enable local energy communities to draw on globally available open-source designs while developing locally adapted solutions that reflect local capacities and environmental conditions.

Without overlooking the tensions and concerns outlined above and centred around the need for the politicisation of community energy projects, and the challenges of their expansion, we turn to the emerging

literature that links energy with the concept of care. We argue that conceptualizing community energy projects as infrastructures of care offers a productive lens through which to rethink their potential to reconfigure socio-environmental transformations and everyday practices.

2.2. From community energy to infrastructures of care

Feminist care ethics offer a crucial lens through which to rethink infrastructure in general and community energy projects in particular. As mentioned in the introduction, Fisher and Tronto's early work [20] defines care as the activities necessary to maintain, continue, and repair the world we inhabit—encompassing bodies, selves, and environments in an interdependent web of life. Later scholars such as Puig de la Bellacasa [44] insist that life itself is inseparable from practices of care: someone or something must always be engaged in acts of maintaining or sustaining, even if such work is invisible or undervalued. As Chatzidakis et al. [45,p.29] point out, recognising our mutual needs to give and receive care “enables us to confront our shared fears of human frailty, rather than project them onto those we label as ‘dependent’”, thereby fostering meaningful forms of communal attachment. In this sense, energy communities foreground caring labour and shared resources, not only by providing more affordable energy but also by holding together social relations, neighbourhood solidarities, and ecological commitments.

Framing energy communities as *infrastructures of care* extends debates on community energy by shifting attention from energy as a purely technical or economic domain to energy as relational, affective and political [46]. Scholars have begun bridging the concept of care with infrastructure, drawing on the wider “infrastructural turn” [47] that sees infrastructure as political, performative and relational, embedded in the routines of everyday life. Carr [46,p. 223] stresses that our capacities to “repair and care for our world and each other are of course profoundly important for adapting to, and coping with, the conditions of planetary breakdown”. In this view, the relationship between infrastructure and care and repair, becomes a crucial dimension of climate adaptation, visible in the growing need to repair failing infrastructures, provide disaster relief, and rebuild after extreme weather events [46]. Alam and Houston [25] advance this line of inquiry by imagining care as an alternative infrastructure and calling for greater attention to feminist ethics of care that foreground individuals as members of social networks bound by mutual responsibility. Other scholars shed light on specific infrastructures as infrastructures of care. For example, Power and Mee [27] explore how housing as infrastructure of care shapes and differentiates the giving and receiving of care, while Williams and Tait [28] explore food systems as vital infrastructures of care essential to sustaining urban life.

Recent scholarship explicitly engages the energy–care nexus [48]. These authors highlight that energy transitions are always relational: decisions about energy generation, distribution, or exclusion involve care toward some communities and environments while neglecting others. For instance, a study of solar power in the Czech Republic, reveals care for ecological habitats and simultaneous disregard for marginalized Roma populations [49]. On the other hand, Kaika and Tsavdaroglou [50] introduce the concept of ‘refugees’ energy commons’, showing how self-organised access to energy was entangled with processes of mutual support, trust, care, and solidarity in a refugee squat in Greece. In general, it is illustrated that retail energy markets are experienced unevenly: energy poor households often face additional hurdles due to limited resources and weaker support networks [51]. Hence, vulnerability, interdependence and responsibility are central to applying care ethics in the energy domain [52]. Bouzarovski [53] connects energy to relations of care and community, by exploring practices within the solidarity economy, particularly around household energy demand. Lucas-Healey et al. [54] see care as an important issue not only to rethink the present energy systems and their maintenance, vulnerability

and disruption, but also to imagine future energy systems grounded on care and reciprocity. Rather than focusing solely on consumption levels or distributive fairness—as in conventional energy justice frameworks—care ethics draw attention to people's capabilities to care for themselves and others under given socio-material conditions.

Cain [55] calls for a deeper engagement with non-Western care-based worldviews, that could enrich the emerging focus of energy research on caring practices beyond domestic settings. Groves et al. [56] similarly argue that ethics of care remain an overlooked concept in energy justice discourses despite its focus on relationality and obligation. Their empirical research suggests that encounters with energy insecurity heighten people's awareness of interdependence in complex energy systems and shed light on underlying power inequalities. Thus, a shift from energy justice to energy ethics by adopting care as an analytical lens is proposed. The emerging literature on care within energy social science foregrounds relational existence within energy webs and recognising interdependence as a basic condition of life can reshape how energy is understood in everyday practice [57]. In that sense, energy transition discourses should centre on the care ethical notion of responsibility. Gherardi and Rodeschini [58,p. 267] similarly suggest that the ethic of care – unlike the ethic of justice – emphasizes the importance of response, it “changes the moral perspective from the question of ‘what is just?’ to the question of ‘how to respond?’”. This makes care a crucial concept for energy projects that seek collective ways of refiguring change and responding to contemporary energy challenges.

Repair and *care*, then, should be understood not as technical fixes [26] but as political acts [59] within energy communities. Care is both infrastructural and affective [60]: it sustains collective resilience while shaping activist subjectivities and relational ways of living [61]. Repair, likewise, is both restorative and reparative: a situated practice involving the *unlearning* of extractive logics and the *rebuilding* of place-based solidarities [62]. Together, care and repair form a political vocabulary of transformation and a dual lens that highlights the often-invisible labours, frequently gendered, racialised or classed, that sustain infrastructure and life itself [63], while foregrounding community agency and knowledge as central to infrastructure's future-making capacities [46]. Energy communities, in this view, are potentially crucial spaces where alternative futures are rehearsed, spaces of collectivisation of energy production and consumption in ways that challenge dominant market logics, where we can reimagine energy as a shared, relational, and socially embedded resource. Centring care in our thinking about energy communities allows us to see energy transition as a matter beyond efficiency, revealing transformative possibilities for reconfiguring not only energy systems but also the everyday urban and communal life bound up with them.

3. Methodology

In this paper, we draw empirical insights from two energy communities: one located in peripheral northwestern Greece and one in London, England. Both operate on cooperative models centred on communally owned and maintained solar panel infrastructures. Their differing spatial contexts, peripheral/regional in the Greek case and metropolitan/urban in the English case, offer an opportunity to examine how community energy practices and care relations are shaped by place-specific socio-geographical settings and infrastructural conditions.

Empirical data were collected between 2023 and 2025 through field visits and 25 semi-structured interviews with different target groups. The interviewees were mainly founders and active members of the two cooperatives and members of supporting organizations that advocate for community energy initiatives in Greece and the UK, offering technical consultancy, legal advice, assistance in recruiting members and raising awareness on energy issues. Other interviewees included policy-makers and residents of the areas engaged in related grassroots communal projects. The interviews were conducted in different stages, and follow-

up online interviews were conducted after the first fieldtrips. Interviews were complemented by analysis of the energy communities' digital communication strategies (websites, newsletters, social media outputs etc.) and informal conversations during site visits, which were recorded in fieldwork notebooks. The interviewees were recruited using the snowball method, starting from the founders of the two energy communities, on the basis of their role, involvement, and expertise. All interview participants were informed about the aims of the research and their voluntary participation prior to the interviews. Ensuring anonymity, we refer to the Greek energy community as ECG and the respective supporting organization as SOG, while the English energy cooperative is referred to as ECE and the respective supporting organization as SOE. It is worth noting that the authors are not members of any of the initiatives, yet their positionality is supportive of the initiatives' cause, with genuine concern for the socio-ecological situation related to this research.

ECE, established in 2011, is a not-for-profit citizen cooperative addressing issues of energy poverty by developing community-owned renewable energy projects. Revenues generated remain within the local area, strengthening local economic resilience and sustainability. ECE is supported by SOE, founded in 2017, currently supporting around 30 community energy groups across the UK. ECG, established ten years later, in 2021, launched its first solar park in 2023, providing electricity for households and small local businesses. ECG's projects are designed for self-consumption rather than for energy sale and the cooperative aims also to develop energy saving strategies within its network. Its creation was supported by SOG, whose mission is to support the transition to democratic and sustainable energy systems and foster the establishment of energy cooperatives.

The data collected from the interviews were then analysed using thematic analysis, and triangulated with the observations from the digital communication, and the informal conversations. The initial thematic analysis identified recurring themes such as the educational role of community energy initiatives, the politicisation of energy communities, particularly in relation to scaling and energy sufficiency, and practices of solidarity and support for marginalized groups. Through this analysis the concept of care emerged as a core issue of the process. During a second round of thematic analysis the data were categorised using Tronto's [29] phases of care as an analytical framework. Empirical insights are mapped onto these phases to examine how community energy projects can be reconceptualised as infrastructures of care. This methodological approach aims to illuminate the potential of community energy initiatives to contribute to broader socio-environmental transformations not only through technical interventions but also through the deeper normative shifts they cultivate in participants' understandings and practices of energy.

4. Community energy in the five phases of care

4.1. Attentiveness - caring about

For Tronto [29,p.34], the first phase of care -caring about- is grounded in attentiveness. It describes the moment when "someone or some group notices unmet caring needs", requiring "a suspension of one's self-interest, and a capacity genuinely to look from the perspective of the one in need". Attentiveness is not only directed outward; it can also concern the recognition of one's own needs and vulnerabilities. In the context of community energy, we argue that this initial phase of care manifests in an attentiveness to the need for environmental change and to a wide range of environmental concerns, such as the need to reduce energy consumption, enhance sustainability, and protect local environments – *their care about the planet*.

While talking about the main strategic objectives of their initiatives and the reasons that led them to found and develop them, our interviewees confirm this centrality of ecological care. A member of SOE clearly states that "*the main motivation is the climate agenda and also*

taking advantage of the energy transition". And similarly, a member of ECG emphasised strongly that they not only "*try to cover local energy needs*" but they are doing it "*in ways that encourage people to think differently about energy*", showing that what drives energy projects is the attentiveness to the need for environmental protection. For both cases, what appears vitally important is that energy communities seek to reframe understandings of energy by explicitly addressing sufficiency and demand. Attentiveness thus also involves reframing everyday understandings of energy, recognising that energy is finite, material, and environmentally consequential.

Especially interviewees from ECG emphasised their strategy to challenge peoples' view of energy as an infinite resource and try to "*understand where energy comes from, what is involved in its production and how we can contribute to addressing climate change*". For the founders and members of ECG, profit was not a primary motivation. As interviewees emphasised, the cooperative is oriented toward self-consumption and explicitly operates beyond monetary incentives: the energy produced is used to meet members' needs rather than being sold on the market. This distinguishes this energy community from other Greek energy communities that mobilise the same legal framework for revenue generation and indicates a stronger emphasis on ecological care and collective provision. In this sense, energy is treated not as a commodity but as a shared resource within the cooperative.

Education and awareness-raising thus become central elements of attentiveness and a crucial motivation for participation. Interviewees repeatedly stressed that environmental awareness becomes more powerful when connected to a local initiative. As a member of SOE argues "*It is very hard to engage people when you talk about a nuclear power station 150 miles away*", but on the contrary it is easier for people to engage "*when a community energy project is installed in a community building and a discussion starts about the energy reductions this would bring*". As they aptly argue "*it is more powerful when it happens at the end of your road*". This perspective led both initiatives to expand their objectives beyond the development of energy infrastructures toward more educational and community-based initiatives. As members of ECE told us they discovered that people who are interested in community energy were also interested in other ecological community activities, like gardening and horticulture. This led them to establish new projects in parallel to their energy community "*where people can stay actively engaged through hands-on participation in gardening, environmental stewardship, and education*". As they explained these new activities are very impactful, with a lot of participants and they plan to continue this trajectory of "*strengthening the bonds between community, sustainability, and renewable energy*". Similarly, interviewees from SOG, described new efforts to address sufficiency and make energy use a more collective and conscious practice, in the energy community's new project that will attempt to shift "*consumption to the times when production is higher*". As they explained this could be done through automation, but also through "*a more educational and awareness-raising way*" to change people's perspectives on energy. As they argue "*we were used to just pressing a button and doing whatever we want, but we should be more aware of that*" because we should "*aim for sufficiency not by producing more but by adapting consumption to production*".

4.2. Responsibility - caring for

The second phase of care is caring for and is grounded in the moral quality of responsibility: "*Once needs are identified, someone or some group has to take on the burden of meeting those needs. This is responsibility, and that is the key moral quality of this second phase*" [29,p. 34]. In the case of community energy projects, this phase becomes visible when people move from *caring about* the planet and the issue of energy, to also actively caring for the *production of community energy* and taking on the burden of making it happen.

The founders and members of the energy communities we interviewed, described the first steps they took to address issues of

consumption and energy use, demonstrating in practice that energy demand must be regulated. For example, interviewees from ECE shared with us some of the concrete steps they undertook during the early years of their project to help local communities reduce their energy consumption and their energy bills. As they explained they first tried to persuade the local community that “*by granting communities more autonomy, people could become agents of change*”. So, over the first year and a half of their project they “*held weekly meetings, raising awareness about energy consumption and engaging directly with residents*”. As a result, they built a relationship of trust with other residents and they were able to access peoples' homes to offer “*free advice on reducing energy bills, switching providers, and installing energy-saving measures*”, accomplishing measurable results, with some residents saving up to 30% on their energy bills that year, which made them more eager to participate in the project's next phases. In the case of ECG, which was introduced much later, the founders had to undergo a long process of legal preparation, while the recruitment of participants was much easier, as it coincided with the rapid rise of energy bills and the cost-of-living crisis, that led people to be open to communal experimentation for alternatives.

In both cases we observe that such efforts often begin from a personal interest or motivation that gradually develops into a collective interest and shared goal, taking people from the phase of “caring about” to the practice of “caring for”. As a founding member of ECE told us they introduced this energy community when their town was in a phase of transition, and people were looking for ideas to shift to urban just solutions. At that time the founder was writing their master thesis on energy communities and this became the inspiration for them and other members of this transition movement to introduce this idea to the local community. As they explain they shared their research and proposed to “*build an energy bank, which would effectively mean generating energy, and using the revenue to deliver social and environmental projects*”. After this they started having weekly meetings in the local pub and after a year they created their energy community. Similarly, a founding member of ECG shared that the need to start working on alternative communal projects started from their own need. As they explained living and working in Greece in a time of crisis, led them to understand that they should look for collective answers to increasing socio-ecological challenges. This led to a number of alternative projects and the founding of their energy community.

These accounts show how responsibility, taking on the burden of organising, informing others, and creating the structures needed for community energy, is a central component of the early stages of these projects. People not only notice unmet needs but commit themselves to addressing them, turning concern into concrete collective action.

4.3. Competence - care giving

The third phase of care, according to Tronto [29,p. 35], is related to competence and is defined as care giving, described as “*assuming responsibility is not yet the same as doing the actual work of care; doing such work is the third phase of caring and requires the moral quality of competence. To be competent to care, given one's caring responsibilities, is not simply a technical issue, but a moral one.*” We argue that this phase follows naturally from the initial formation of a community energy project and relates to the ability, and commitment, of alternative energy initiatives to address social inequalities and energy poverty. In this context, competence becomes operationalized as the actual provision of *care giving to vulnerable groups*.

Our interviewees from SOE confirmed that many of their member groups engage in such practices to support struggling households. As they explained some groups give advice to individual householders, especially when people struggle to pay their energy bills due to their financial situation or during specific extreme periods, like the pandemic or the ongoing cost-of-living crisis. As they told us “*energy advice in the UK when available, is very complex*” and many people “*especially older people or those who are digitally compromised, had difficulties navigating this*

information”. This is where some energy projects help in giving specific energy advice or even having “*volunteers picking the phone and negotiating with energy companies for a better deal or help with energy efficiency projects to reduce your bills*”.

Interviewees in both England and Greece explicitly recognised the social inequalities embedded in national energy systems and sought to address them through their initiatives. As a representative of a UK supporting organization noted, “*often the people who need energy measures the most are the least informed*”. Interviewees from ECE similarly underscored the structural inequalities of fuel poverty, claiming specifically that “*poor people in the UK, people in fuel poverty, pay the most for their energy*”. They framed energy vulnerability as shaped by intersecting racialised and class-based inequalities that are frequently reduced to technical or legislative issues, thereby obscuring the broader socio-political drivers of energy deprivation. Addressing these structural inequalities was described as a central objective of their work.

Similarly, interviewees from ECG mentioned that one of their key future targets is to make the cooperative and other energy cooperatives in Greece more accessible to the most disadvantaged communities and households. As one member told us the entrance fee for their energy community is a substantial amount of money, which means that their members are not poor. As they explain “*members are not very rich – because if they were they wouldn't really care – but they are also not working-class people*”. This is an issue they would like to tackle in the future, finding solutions for poorer residents to be able to take part in the energy community, even if they don't have the money for the investment. What they are actually able to do at the moment is to give a small percentage of the produced energy for free to some energy vulnerable families, giving them the opportunity to participate in their solar infrastructures without having to pay the entrance fee. Nevertheless, as they stress this is not a solution and, in the future, they would try to invent a funding or lending tool to make the energy community accessible for all working-class people is a substantial amount of money.

These examples illustrate how competence, understood as the actual delivery of care, becomes central in community energy projects' attempts to reduce energy inequalities. While structural barriers remain significant, both cooperatives are engaged in ongoing efforts to reach and support households most affected by energy poverty, demonstrating the moral and practical dimensions of care giving within community energy infrastructures.

4.4. Responsiveness - care receiving

The fourth phase of care in Tronto's [29,p. 35] framework is centred on responsiveness and is defined as care receiving. Tronto describes this as follows: “*Once care work is done, there will be a response from the person, group, animal, plant, environment, or thing that has been cared for. Observing that response, and making judgments about it (for example, whether the care given was sufficient, successful, or complete?) requires the moral quality of responsiveness. The person cared for need not be the one who completes the process of responding, but some response is necessary. And the response will often involve noting that new needs emerge as the past ones are met, thus the process continues*”. In the energy communities we explored, this phase appears in the period after the energy infrastructure has been built, when the cooperative evaluates what has been achieved and identifies new needs, and is identified as *care receiving from other members*.

In both cases this phase functions as a feedback loop in which founders and members show how they remain responsive through a care receiving process. This reflects an alternative way of thinking about technologies, one that pays attention to the longevity of the infrastructure and ensures that the local community can properly maintain it, sustaining a social relation of care over time. Members of SOG pointed out that their work is an ongoing process, that includes both the maintenance of the infrastructures and the social relations that are related to them, claiming that the fact that they built two photovoltaic stations

does not mean that “now everything is done and is static”. As they explain they still have to visit the infrastructure sites, solve any issues that may arise, and continue to plan educational programs and new projects. Similarly, interviewees from the ECE noted that they work in an open and participatory way, remaining accessible to the local community and trying to implement a genuinely grassroots process. They emphasised the importance of remaining responsive to participants' feedback, noting the need for “regular interactions” to sustain genuine grassroots engagement and to include local communities in meaningful ways. As they aptly argued “grassroots is an analogy”, that implies “really in the ground”, highlighting the importance of ongoing, place-based involvement.

In this process of feedback and responsiveness, founders are usually also members of the energy communities, and they also receive care, apart from giving. One of the founding members of ECG that we interviewed shared their own experience from the first period of the project implementation. As they explained, after introducing a digital system that measures consumption and production they “realized that in my house we had very high consumption, compared to another member who has pretty much the same characteristics and needs”. This realisation led the interviewee to ask the other member about their energy consumption patterns, in order to understand what they were doing differently. This interweaving of energy communities' practices with personal relationships of sharing experiences and advice constitutes another manifestation of care. It positions founders not only as providers but also as recipients of care, creating a reciprocal loop of responsiveness that values knowledge beyond expert-led perspectives.

4.5. Plurality, communication, trust and respect; solidarity - caring with

The fifth phase of care was Tronto's [29,p. 23] most recent addition, caring with. This phase centres on concepts such as plurality, communication, trust, respect and solidarity. This process is an important aspect of care described as: “Caring with. This final phase of care requires that caring needs and the ways in which they are met need to be consistent with democratic commitments to justice, equality, and freedom for all.” This phase is particularly important for energy communities, which aim to be open, democratic, and just, and to enhance energy democracy and energy governance as commons, demonstrated as caring with each other and like-minded initiatives. As members of ECG explained, anyone can join their initiative as long as they agree with the core principles of cooperativism and the ideology of not-for-profit action. As they explain “People who want to join must agree with that. We don't aim to maximise benefit, we aim to cover our needs.”. The energy community works as a cooperative, with the logic of one member- one vote, while its highest decision-making body is the general assembly. The participation is voluntary and open, without any discrimination and the objective of the initiative is to prioritize community benefits, education, and raising awareness on energy crisis and climate change. Similarly, ECE values communication and trust, showing a long-term commitment in grassroots' mobilisation and open democratic participation. This closely relates to the enhancement of energy democracy by prioritising participatory governance and communal needs in energy production and consumption.

In both cases, the energy communities operate in collaboration with other like-minded initiatives and in solidarity with other organizations and networks, coordinating and networking their local practices. This is the role of the supporting organizations in both cases, that – among other activities - advocate for higher-level representation capable of influencing national and supranational policy making. Interviewees from the supporting organization in Greece explained the importance of their role also because “The energy market is highly regulated and everything is vulnerable to changes in legislation”. In that sense, they “have to be on top of things and constantly push for political support”. More specifically they explained that they act as advocates for energy communities and they “try to include them in every new regulation and law on energy”.

Lately, they formed a coalition of energy communities in Greece, and joining another coalition operating at a European level would make their influence even stronger. This shows how energy communities and alternative energy projects do not always aim to scale up, but usually grow in a scale out, or scale wide logic, aiming to multiply their influence through the emergence of more projects with relevant objectives and ideology. In parallel, in both cases the founders build long-term collaborations with other like-minded initiatives, including community projects, cooperatives, shared community spaces and more. This shows that the solidarity between members of each energy community, among different energy communities, and with other like-minded initiatives is a crucial part of their development and influence.

4.6. Results overview

In the following table, we summarise the findings mentioned in the previous section, and we show how the five phases of care are manifested in the two energy communities (See Table 1):

5. Discussion

This paper rethinks community energy projects as infrastructures of care, drawing insights from two energy communities in Greece and England. By tracing how these initiatives care about the planet, care for community-led energy production, give care to the most vulnerable, receive care from each other, stay open for the participants' feedback and care with one another and like-minded initiatives in democratic and solidaristic ways, we demonstrate that community energy is best understood as a caring process rather than a solely technical intervention. Such a lens moves beyond conventional framings of energy as a matter

Table 1
Summary of main findings.

Phases of care	Community energy implementation	Main observations
Attentiveness	Care about the planet	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Main motivation was climate change • Energy as a commons, not an infinite resource • Education and raising awareness on environmental issues
Responsibility	Caring for the production of community energy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Needed a long phase of preparation for legal issues and members' recruitment • Started as a personal interest and became a collective motivation
Competence	Care giving to vulnerable groups	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Give energy advice to most vulnerable groups • Reveal race, class and other social inequalities in energy system • Attempt to support energy vulnerable households, even if this is not always possible
Responsiveness	Care receiving from other members	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Remain open to feedback, ready to change and add projects- genuinely grassroots • The role of care giver and receiver is interchangeable between founders and members
Plurality, communication, trust and respect; solidarity	Caring with each other and like-minded initiatives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Democratic, open and participatory values and processes • Solidarity with other energy communities and other like-minded initiatives in their localities and beyond

of technology, efficiency or economics, highlighting instead the relational, ethical and political work that underpins grassroots renewable energy initiatives. It reveals energy communities not merely as reactive responses to the energy crisis, but as prefigurative spaces where counter-hegemonic values are rehearsed and enacted, aligning with scholarship situating grassroots energy projects within broader socio-environmental struggles [19,37,43].

Across both empirical cases, “caring about” emerges as a foundational moment in which environmental and climate concerns motivated collective mobilisation, while localised infrastructures and participatory ownership render abstract climate debates tangible by embedding them in everyday geographies. Importantly, both case studies reframed energy demand as a political and ethical question, echoing debates on energy sufficiency and the limits of growth-oriented logics [37,39]. These orientations connect the practical work of energy communities to broader ‘politics of possibility’ for environmental change [18,37,64] and resonate with findings that participation in energy projects is strongly shaped by environmental values and sustainability commitments [65]. Attentiveness to environmental limits thus becomes an entry point for reconfiguring normative understandings of energy, challenging its treatment as an infinite commodity and situating it instead within relations of interdependence and planetary care.

The phase of “caring for” was visible in founders’ willingness to assume responsibility for reshaping local energy practices. In both cases, they undertook the organisational, logistical and emotional labour necessary to build community energy infrastructures, while activities ranging from sustained community meetings to door-to-door support and educational programmes illustrate how care is mobilised as a collective response to systemic neglect [66,67]. The findings further show that personal motivations often catalysed this responsibility, which then became a shared collective commitment, enabling grassroots action to address locally and regionally specific needs, frequently in places where such interventions are most needed [68]. In this sense, responsibility is enacted through everyday practices that embed energy systems within community life, while remaining shaped by distinct national regulatory environments and political economies.

The third phase, “care giving”, underscores how competence is enacted through interventions addressing energy poverty and structural inequalities. In both cases, energy communities extend their activities beyond energy production to support vulnerable households, increasingly incorporating social support functions [9]. At the same time, our cases also reveal a key tension noted in the literature: participation often requires financial capital, time and technical knowledge and community energy initiatives may therefore reproduce inequalities by relying predominantly on middle-class involvement [10,19]. Deprived communities often lack the time and resources needed to initiate or join such community schemes [69]. “Care giving” thus becomes a site where community energy initiatives negotiate the contradictions between their emancipatory goals and the structural barriers shaping participation.

The phase of “care receiving” illuminates how energy communities remain open to feedback, learning and adaptation, reinforcing the relational dimension of infrastructures of care. Research participants emphasised the importance of continuous interaction, maintenance, and reflexive adjustment of practices, showing how these infrastructures evolve in dialogue with their users rather than remaining static artefacts, attending to the durability and lived experience of socio-technical systems [27]. These processes also transform participants’ subjectivities: members become more aware of their consumption patterns, more attuned to interdependence and more embedded in networks of mutual learning. The exchange of experiences and advice blurs the distinction between care givers and care receivers, positioning them in reciprocal roles and valuing situated knowledge that emerges from everyday energy practices.

Finally, “caring with” underscores the inherently political character of community energy. Both cases operate under cooperative models that prioritize democratic control, situating their projects within debates on

energy commons, energy democracy and post-growth transformations [43]. Their efforts to scale through networks, coalitions and supporting organizations suggest that locally grounded initiatives can reverberate across scales, contributing to wider structural change [18], deepening citizen engagement through democratic participation, and reimagining energy provision not as a profit-making activity but as common wealth [67,70]. Rather than pursuing large-scale replication, both communities adopt forms of horizontal and vertical scaling that seek to preserve their democratic ethos, resonating with calls for cosmological approaches that combine global knowledge with local autonomy [42]. These projects can also be seen through a diverse economies lens as opening post-capitalistic possibilities [19,68], where practices of care are entangled with commons-based and community-led forms of provisioning [71,72]. In this way, “caring with” becomes an expression of solidaristic politics that links local energy practices and struggles to transnational movements for climate justice and energy democracy, reflecting dynamics identified in grassroots mobilisations against environmental and infrastructural injustice [8,14,73–76].

Subsequently, this paper makes three key contributions to energy social science. First, it introduces care ethics as an analytical framework for community energy. By operationalising Tronto’s phases of care, the paper demonstrates that community energy practices are underpinned by forms of attentiveness, responsibility, competence, responsiveness and solidarity that remain underexplored in existing scholarship [77]. This shifts the analysis beyond technical processes to engage the interpersonal, normative and ethical dimensions of energy production and consumption, linking community energy to wider debates on environmental care, climate change, commons and sufficiency beyond economic growth.

Second, the paper advances debates on energy justice, energy democracy and energy citizenship by showing that care reconfigures participation. This challenges models of energy citizenship centred on voluntarism and individual behavioural change, foregrounding instead the shared ethical and practical labour required to address energy vulnerability. At the same time, it highlights internal tensions and contradictions that shape community energy, including risks of reproducing exclusions, uneven care work, the challenges of scaling without erasing local specificity and the ambiguities of operating within growth-oriented energy systems [78]. The focus on care further highlights these tensions by examining how alternative energy projects seek to address issues of race, class and social inequality, even where structural obstacles and practical barriers make this difficult and increase the risk of middle-class capture.

Third, by drawing on two cases situated in distinct regulatory, economic and cultural contexts (Greece and the UK), the paper shows how infrastructures of care emerge across divergent settings. The cases reflect different trajectories of community energy development: the UK has a longer standing tradition and a larger participant base, while the Greek initiative is more recent and operates at a smaller scale. Rather than pursuing a detailed comparison, our analysis adopts a relational approach that traces how similar care practices take shape under contrasting conditions. This allows for the identification of shared dynamics alongside context-specific constraints and demonstrates both the adaptability of care-based energy practices and ways institutional, temporal and socio-economic contexts shape their evolution.

Taken together, these contributions position community energy not merely as sites of technical experimentation but as contested arenas in which socio-environmental futures are materially and politically negotiated. By foregrounding care, the paper shows that energy communities can contribute not only to immediate relief from energy poverty and climate vulnerability but also to longer-term shifts in how energy is understood, valued and governed, albeit within the constraints of existing regulatory frameworks. As infrastructures of care, they have the potential to cultivate capabilities, solidarities and democratic practices that open pathways toward more equitable, socially embedded and environmentally attuned energy systems, while remaining dependent on

sustained collective labour and context-specific support. Their work points to the possibility of reconfiguring everyday life around principles of sufficiency, interdependence and collective responsibility, without presuming that such transformations are linear or universally accessible. In this sense, community energy initiatives both respond to and expose the impacts of the energy crisis, prefiguring alternative models of provisioning and governance, while also resonating with broader debates on commons-based, non-hierarchical forms of organising and on the multiple geographies through which more liveable, just, caring, and solidaristic futures are produced [79,80].

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Danai Liodaki: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Conceptualization. **Elia Apostolopoulou:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Conceptualization.

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Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

The data that has been used is confidential.

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